

**DRUMMONDEANDO BETWEEN ANJOS TORTOS AND TRONCHOS:
AN ANALYSIS OF THE “SEVEN FACES” OF THE SONG “ANJOS
TRONCHOS” BY CAETANO VELOSO**

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ABSTRACT: The poem named “Poema de sete faces”, by Carlos Drummond de Andrade has been paraphrasing and parodied since his publication. Recently, the Brazilian singer Caetano Veloso released the song “Anjos Tronchos” in his new album *Meu Coco* (2021), this song is a re-reading of the famous work of Drummond. The actuality of the composition directly dialogues with the poem, besides to bring other intertexts that made the song a sharp criticism of the actuality way of life, the social media influence and his domination under human beings, but without forgetting the benefits of the internet. As an artistic expression the poem and the song have no compromise in portraying the real, that's why both arts can be faithful with their story. This research tries to investigate the actuality of the song in comparison with the poem and his time, through an inter(trans)text interpretation, non restrictive, also considering the Umberto Eco theory in *Os Limites da Interpretação*, jointly with theorists as Octávio Paz, Affonso Romano de Sant'Anna and Antonio Cândido. The topic will be analyzed from a sociological and historical point of view by theorists as Wécio Pinheiro Araujo and Shoshana Zuboff.

Keywords: Carlos Drummond; Caetano Veloso; dialogs; criticism; social media.

*Time is my matter, the present time,
present men, present life
Carlos Drummond de Andrade*

Introduction - The Gauche poet and his time

In *Drummond: o gauche no tempo*, Affonso Romano de Sant'Anna (2008, p. 14) shows us that there is a character in the dramatic structure of this poet's work: “... (the gauche poet) disguised in heteronyms (José, Carlos, Carlito, K., Robinson Crusoe, etc.), which describes an action in time and space conceived as a *continuum*.” In this sense, it is possible to perceive that

time is the great subject of the poet and all his concern comes from it, as can be seen in the above passage.

Regarding the relationship between poetry and its time, Octávio Paz (1982, p. 11) states that poetry is circular as something that closes in on itself (self-sufficient), while prose is linear. Thus, rhythm is a natural condition of the human being and that precedes the word itself, justifying the existence of myths, songs and other poetic expressions in any and all society. In this way, it is perceived that poetry works as a circular unit that highlights the tension and union between sounds, images and rhythms that show what the lyrical self thinks of itself and the world that surrounds it. In view of this, we can frame Drummond's work among some modern poets who can be seen as historians who participate in the society in which they are inserted, transmitting the marks of their time without, however, having any commitment to reality (WELLEK & WARREN, 2003, p.11).

Although uncommitted to the real, the poet cannot get rid of his time and space, which makes him an instrument for transmitting this reality, even if figuratively. Since:

At each moment [man] wants to fulfill himself as a totality, and each of his hours is a monument to a momentary eternity. There is no remedy for escaping your temporal condition, but to submerge yourself more fully in time. The only way you can defeat him is to merge with him. It does not reach eternal life, but creates a unique moment that will never be repeated and, in this way, gives rise to history (PAZ, 1982, p.190 - 191).

Thus, Drummond's poetry is perceived as a portrait of his time and that immortalizes moments and thoughts as on a canvas, putting the lyrical character/self in evidence in order to seek the reader's identification with the "pains of the world" that permeate his life. poetic.

In the present analysis, we will seek to observe the presence of the "marks of its time" that appear in the drummondian poem *Poema de sete faces* (1930) and in the lyrics of the song "Anjos tronchos" (2021) by Caetano Veloso. In this course of analysis, we will observe other poems/song lyrics that establish a dialogic relationship with the 1930 poem, each one as a portrait of its own time.

Thus, in an attempt to capture, in a non-reductive way, the essence of this poetics and the others that will be presented throughout the analysis, we seek subsidies in the analysis proposal presented by Umberto Eco in the book *Os Limits da Interpretação*. According to this theorist, there are three questions that have based the theories of recent years regarding the analysis of the literary text: "What did the author mean? What did the text mean regardless of what the author intends? What does the reader find in the text "in relation to their own systems of meaning and/or in relation to their own desires, drives, will" (ECO, 1995, p.7). Each of

these questions proved to reduce the broad interpretative possibility which should take into account all three questions, but without losing sight of the text itself. Thus, for this theorist, the interpreter's initiative is to propose on the text a possibility that passes through the legitimizing sieve of the text itself. In this way, a proposal of intertextuality is built based on the triple intention (model-author/text/model-reader). In view of this, the reader/analyst is “free to risk all the interpretations he wants, but obliged to give up when the text does not approve of his most libidinal daring” (ECO, 1995, p.16).

Therefore, the interpretation, especially with regard to modern and contemporary texts, must take into account the multiple dialogic possibilities with other texts, a fact that requires greater attention on the part of the reader.

Intertextuality and parody over time

Within this perspective, it is crucial that the interpretive process takes into account intertextuality as a process of superimposition of a literary text on another that can be noticed directly or indirectly, so that the influence of a text on another text can come from different ways, which requires extra attention. In the rewriting of the poem, it is possible to experience a freedom of recreation that reveals the concept of paraphrase as a process that does not intend to copy or reproduce, but to produce something new, different, without losing sight of the poem that motivated it.

Similarly, parody is defined by intertextuality, however it differs from paraphrase by being marked by the displacement of a comic or ironic motivation and by the antagonism of voices designed in critical opposition to the original text. The "discontinuity" of this type of text attracts the radical literary movements of the beginning of the 20th century. XX as Futurism and Dadaism. SANT'ANNA (1985, p. 7) observes that "the frequency with which parodistic texts appear testifies that contemporary art delights in an exercise of language where language folds back on itself in a game of mirrors".

Paes (1990, p. 59), in turn, considers that the joke poem is the “touchstone of the irreverent and iconoclastic modernism of 22”. In this sense, it should be noted that humor was not a well-accepted element in traditional “serious” poetry, however it became widely accepted and even recommended after the week of the 22nd. Sant'Anna (1985, p. 61) , theorizing about the difference between parody and paraphrase, identifies that both are recreations that function as an act of appropriation; there being “a displacement of the ownership of the text, the elimination of the owners of writing, the possibility for each creator to manipulate the real of the text according to their critical inclinations”.

From this perspective, it can be seen that Drummond's *Poema de Sete Faces* served as an inspiration for several rewritings since its publication in 1930 (*Some Poetry*). In most cases, parody occurs through a thematic alteration of the basic text, contrary to the idea originally expressed, being able to make use of irony and satire to highlight the tone of criticism and promote reflection. The present analysis seeks, in a non-reductive way, to propose an analysis of how the process of some of these rewritings takes place.

the many angels

One of the best-known rewritings of Drummond's poem, which yielded many analyzes and publications, was the poem *With a poetic license* (1976), by Adélia Prado, whose very title suggests the parodistic tone of the composition. Adélia contradicts the thematic proposal of a basic text based on the type of angel that predicts the destiny of the two lyrical selves. In Drummond we have a crooked Angel, who lives in the shadows ¹², and who determines that Carlos will be *gauche* ¹³ in life, while Adélia's rewriting presents us with a slender angel ¹⁴, one of those who play the trumpet ¹⁵, who prophesies that the lyrical self must carry the flag, as to usher in a new era for the female gender. It is possible to perceive the intertext both in the semantic field and in the syntactic field, since the structures are parallel, as can be seen in the comparison:

When I was born, a crooked angel
Of those who live in the shade
He said: Go, Carlos! be gauche in life

When I was born a slender angel,
of those who play the trumpet, announced:
will carry the flag.

It is noticed, therefore, that Drummond's poem presents the lyrical self as a displaced and strange being, as well as the angel who predestinates him, as if there was an identification between them, just as it is possible to perceive the same type of identification in the poem by Drummond. Adélia, which presents an outstanding lyrical self that is presented through an angel whose beauty shines and who comes to announce a great change for women who, through the figure of the poet, will raise this flag, the flag of women's rights. There is a transposition of meaning and a critical tone that gives the text a parodistic character.

¹²Shadow is in opposition to light, representing everything that is unreal, elusive and subject to change. In psychoanalysis, it can represent the inferior traits of character, everything that the person refuses to admit or recognize, but always imposes itself on him. (CHEVALIER & GHEERBRANT, 1998, p. 842)

¹³From the French language, it means "left". In the poem it works as a metaphor for someone who is strange, different, walks unlike most people.

¹⁴Modern/contemporary symbol of beauty imposed, in particular, on women.

¹⁵Instrument used to announce major events. (CHEVALIER & GHEERBRANT, 1998, p. 910)

Bosi considers that the image is not modeled on the object's way of being, even if it is apprehended:

Because the imagined is, at the same time, given and constructed. Given, as matter. But constructed, as a form for the subject. Given: it does not depend on our will to receive the sensations of light and color that the world provokes. But constructed: the image results from a complicated process of perceptive organization that develops from early childhood (BOSI, 2004, p.22).

Thus, it is possible to notice that each text reflects a reality which is intrinsically related to its time. We can see the incompatibility of Adélia's text for the time of the 1930s, when Drummond's text was published. In this way, the texts are not modeled on the beings who produced them, in addition to reflecting the image of a masculine social construction suitable for the 1930s, as well as the adequacy of the female role for the year 1976, a period in which the struggle for women's rights was at the center of social and political discussions in Brazil.

Another rewriting of Drummond's poem occurs in the lyrics of the song *Ado o fim* (1978), by Chico Buarque, which presents a naughty angel, who predestines the lyrical self to be wrong, but he does not accept the prophecy and promises to continue trying to change his destiny. “*until the end*”. Thus, both parodies follow a semantic and syntactic pattern, but which, at the same time, goes against the original meaning of the poem in a critical and ironic way:

When I was born, a crooked angel
Of those who live in the shade
He said: Go, Carlos! be gauche in life

When I was born a naughty angel came
the annoying cherub
And decreed that I was destined
to be wrong like this

It is crucial to note that, in the three texts, the poetic images are extremely personal and refer specifically to the birth of each of their lyrical selves and the prophecies uttered by angels (specific to each lyrical selves) to these poetic *personas*. The first two words of each poem demonstrate that it is about a specific moment and takes us back to fairy tales and stories from Greek mythology as in the stories of Psyche, Narcissus, Oedipus and others whose fate was sealed at birth.

In the sequence, appears the figure of the angel sometimes crooked, sometimes slender, sometimes naughty, but all with the same mission to predict the fate of these newborns who appear almost as a reflection of the angel himself. Throughout the readings, it is clear that the destiny of the three lyrical selves is closely linked to the poetic work, as if they were chosen for the noble and, sometimes, ungrateful mission of writing poetry and composing songs with all

the weights of this noble craft. , as a modern “profession of faith”. But the parodies don't stop there, following crooked and crooked paths until the end.

Between crooked angels and trunks

Following the same line of rewriting, Caetano Veloso releases, in 2021, the album *Meu coco* , whose single and “Anjos *tronchos* ” works as a parody of Drummond’s poem, as can be seen in the excerpt transcribed below:

Some angels from Silicon Valley
Of those who live in the dark in full light
They said you'll be virtuous in addiction
From the screens of blues more than blues

Now my story is a dense algorithm
That sells sale to real sellers
My neurons gained another rhythm
And more and more and more and more and more

(...)

Leading clowns sprouted macabre
In the empire and in its vast backyards
To which millenary empires see
Armed with full controls

Angels already mi or bi or trillionaires
They only command their mi, bi, trillions
And we, when we're not suckers
We hear Shoenberg, Webern, Cage, songs

Ah, beautiful brunette, you are here
No skin, screen to screen
We are there

(...)

But there are poems like never before
Or as some poet dreamed
In the times when there were times ago
And I will, why not?
I will, why not? I will go

Some angels from Silicon Valley
They touched the smallest grain deep
And while we wonder from the start
Miss Eilish does everything in the bedroom with her brother

In the first stanza you can already see the points that differentiate this parody from the others, because here we have not one, but "*some tronchos angels*"¹⁶ whose adjective can refer to the absence of wings or supernatural powers, since they are men who believe they are angels capable of predicting destinies through data manipulation. The identification between these angels and the lyrical self is due to the fact that they are all human beings. In this way, these angels are characterized throughout the text as the mi, bi or trillionaire entrepreneurs in the technological field of "*Silicon Valley*"¹⁷, who determine the future not only of the lyrical self, but of all of "*us*" (4th stanza of the excerpt) through the algorithms that dominate our neurons which have gained a new rhythm, little by little, "more and more". In the pun constructed through the rhyme "algorithm"/"rhythm" it is visible how these angels control the rhythm of the thoughts of these "virtuosi in vice" of blue screens, directing us to the abyss of consumerism and the domination of other areas of the world. social and political life ("*Leading clowns sprouted macabre/ In the empire and in its vast backyards/ As they see millenary empires/ Equipped with total controls*").

In addition, these beings (angels/men) live in the "dark in full light", symbolizing the activity of limitless domination that they exercise without control of any nature, acting in an obscure way, although it is known to all. The prophecy, built from a play on words that explores alliteration ("*will be virtuous in addiction*") , demonstrates that the more successful in the addiction to "*blue screens*" , the better; that is, the more addicted, the better for them, as the greater the exposure to pop art/advertising will be, which will determine their profit. At this point, the conflicting theme between the first three texts and the current one can be seen, as there is no identification between the Angel and men, except for the supposed humanity; nor is there an identification between the prediction and the nature of the angel, as occurred in the previous texts, since they themselves do not usually use the products they offer (social media).

Making use of puns and wordplay, Caetano shows us all his ironic/critical potential, already presented since the times of Tropicalismo. In the passage "*sell sale to sellers*", the pun on the verb Vendar hides the substantivation of "*sale*" (papa eye) in a double game with the verb sell in the imperative so that both prevent users from perceiving the domination that occurs in full light, in an obscure way (in the dark), without being noticed. They are new angels of new and dark times.

¹⁶ Crooked, unfinished, badly made, crude, mutilated, crippled, truncated, deprived of any limb.

¹⁷ Nickname given to the region of California (USA) which is home to the largest companies producing electronic circuits and which serves as the headquarters of large startups with a global reach (Google, Apple and Facebook, among others), with specialized labor provided by the University of Stanford which is in the region.

New times, new prophecies

It is important to note that there are 91 years between the basic composition and Caetano's text. This temporal distance brought many social changes that are noticeable in the composition of 2021, as well as the difference between that and Adélia's text regarding the role of women in society, always perceiving the composition as a mirror of its time.

The documentary “The Networks Dilemma” (2020), by *Netflix*, reports the experience of some of the former collaborators of the main companies in the field (*Pinterest, Facebook, Twitter, Google and YouTube*), making it clear to the common user how the operations of these companies capture the data of these users and monitor their activities, manipulating the search paths and access to the networks. This filter is done through personalized algorithms based on the accesses of each user. The word “algorithm”, coined by the Persian mathematician Muhammad ibs Musa al-Khwarizmi, refers, in the adaptation for computer science, to the combination of a predicted set of “well-defined instructions for the solution of a problem, such as a performance of a calculation in a finite number of steps”¹⁸

In recent years, internet access has intensified and, according to Zuboff (2021), “information and communication technologies are more widespread than electricity, reaching three of the seven billion people in the world” (p. 16) . This factor was potentiated during the Covid 19 pandemic, whose confinement and social distancing imposed new means of connecting to the other. Thus, algorithms and the manipulation of what is accessed on the networks became a common discussion in academia and outside it, especially after the allegations of fraud by Fake News in the US and Brazilian presidential elections.

We see, therefore, a new process of formation of the subject in this new model of society that privileges the virtual for several factors. According to Araújo:

the process of formation of the subject takes place under the sign of the contradiction located at the heart of its ontos, that is, in the relationship between content and constituting form of the being as a subject, which in the digital age presents itself as a deformed version of social experience, since it copies itself in a spectacular imagery version (Debord), while also freezing and distracting consciousness through sensation (Türcke) provoked by the frantic firing of imagery stimuli. (2021, p. 468)

¹⁸ <http://www.ihu.unisinos.br/78-noticias/570310-a-silenciosa-dominacao-por-algoritmos> , accessed on 12/03/21 10 am

In this process, the algorithms assume management, “guided by the logic of the commodity in the historical context of neoliberalism” (IDEM, p. 468), as a form of constant surveillance by the economic system over the experience of human beings, taking away from the individual their sovereignty through a pseudo-freedom disguised in a false individual choice that is usually wrongly defined as “my opinion”.

In this way, social experience takes on a new form, which Eugênio Bucci calls the “imaginary super-industry”:

The physiognomy of our era has the texture, consistency, nature – and, at the same time, the fleetingness, evanescence and volatility – of a scene that glistens on the electronic screen. What is there is what it is. The mutant figures that insinuate themselves and dissolve into digital mirages have the authority of indices of truth: what actually exists wears them in order to be seen and, clothed in them, does not need to be real to exist. History is not written, history is drawn (BUCCI, 2021, 23)

Faced with this social experience, Caetano Veloso composes the song “Anjos Tronchos”, making direct reference to the domination that these “Silicon Valley Angels” have been exercising over human beings who “allow” this domination or, otherwise, find themselves excluded. of this new social model, because, according to Araújo:

Through the digital image, technology ideologically favors the domination of the social logic of the commodity, not exactly over individuals, but, in fact, inside and around them. Digitization surrounds and fills this screen-subject in its ways of being, since it makes the pure imagetic positivity of the spectacle (spectacle) prevail and the naturalization of processes that, in their contents and forms, are not natural, but, on the contrary, are socially constructed and culturally conditioned. Thus, the social experience is lived in a deformed way in their conduct and social practices.(ARAÚJO, 2021, p.468)

Therefore, domination does not resemble domination, or rather, it is as if the individual's influence over the algorithms gave him a false sense of power of choice, making this "voluntary servitude" more pleasant and fully acceptable, being able to reach the most different fields of social relations imperceptibly. These are the times of the truncated Angels who are devoid of the aura of sacredness. They resemble the Greek gods in predicting the fate of men, but they are as human as we are. They believe in their own sacralization given by the financial power that grants them the right to manipulate the fate of thousands of people.

Final Thoughts - Only art saves us, will save us

Thus, it is possible to perceive a reasonable distinction between the angels of the 20th century and the angels of the 21st century described in the texts analyzed here. The three angels of the 20th century, from the basic text and the first two parodies analyzed, demonstrate the personalism of the works, as Drummond's angel determines that he will be *gauche* in life and, throughout the text, this lyrical self demonstrates the feeling of helplessness experienced by the abandonment of God, recognizing himself as a man (*My God, why did you abandon me/If you knew that I was not God*), making clear the distance between the sacred and the human. Adelia's angel, on the other hand, grants a prosperous future to the lyrical self who has the sacred mission of carrying the flag, being an illuminated one (by the divine light) who will have the role of clearing the terrain of male privileges to impose rights. of the women. On the other hand, Chico's angel, following the tradition of his many characters who live roguely on the sidelines, determines that his lyrical self will not succeed in life and, although he constantly fights against this prophecy, the sacred imposes itself on the human, offering no other way. except to keep fighting, even if you don't succeed in your merely human possibilities. Therefore, regardless of the fate of each one, manipulation comes from the angels who are divine beings capable of predicting the irremediable future of each one, like modern Oedipus.

Caetano's text, however, presents us with a new type of angel/man who considers himself to be God and who thinks he is capable of dominating crowds in the service of his own interest, manipulating personal, social and even national destinies. On the other hand, there are men who allow themselves to be manipulated through “sales” that obscure reality, in a passive acceptance. However, at this point, the men of the lyrics of the song (from 2021) differ diametrically from the previous men/women, as they (men of the lyrics of Caetano's song) would have the possibility of not accepting the prediction/destiny, being able to choose to receive or not what was destined for him, different from the “all bad” lyrical self of Chico, who has no way of imposing his will on what was destined for him. In Caetano's song, however, there is a false sensation of following his own will, his “opinion” and not feeling manipulated by these angels who act in the dark in full light. In this way, the men of 2021 do not feel obliged to accept it, as it is not a sacred prediction, but they accept it almost without question, of their own free will, as they are blindfolded to reality.

Although the lyrics of the song (2021) make a critical analysis of this domination exercised by *startups* and algorithms, the lyrical self points out the positive points of the networks with the democratization of art as a means of salvation “*But there are poems like*

never / Or like some poet dreamed”, referring to the many poems available on the Net as any poet never dreamed of in those “*times ago*” . At another point he talks about the reach of art through the internet when talking about Arnold Schönberg (1874 – 1951), Anton Webern (1883 – 1945), John Cage (1912 – 1992), avant-garde composers who innovated and challenged the world order, which would not be accessible were it not for the internet, indicating that this can be a recipe for times when “*we are not suckers*” .

It is noticed that the counterpoint between present and past is evident in the lyrics of Caetano's song through the intertextuality that goes beyond *O poema de sete faces* , as it is possible to perceive the reference to the song *Falar a Verdade* by the band Cidade Negra (*We are there*) , referring to this user of the networks that is always available. In another passage, the intertext occurs with the song of his own authorship, referring to the beginning of his career with the song *Alegria joy* and the movement of Tropicália in the verses “ *E eu vou, por que não?/ eu vou, por que não? ? I go* ”, referring to the same basic idea of the verses of Cidade Negra, whose questioning and answer are usually a constant in the daily life of internet users, after all... “ *why not?* ”.

As can be seen, for Caetano, art is the point of contact of this new being with his humanity, so the song ends with references to Miss Eilish who produced her album with the help of her brother inside her own room with the use of the same technology that imprisons, but which here freed, as this production made her the youngest artist to be nominated for the Grammy Awards in the main categories. While he himself (Caetano) needed to set up a studio at home to produce the album *Meu coco* during the pandemic. Therefore, Caetano shows us both sides of the internet, in a constant movement of imprisoning and freeing, making clear the option that men have in the face of these “ *Angels tronchos* ”.

In this way, it is possible to notice the circularity of Caetano's thought that since the beginning of his career points to the savior power of art as Nietzsche declared "We have art in order not to die before the truth". In this sense, the lyrics of a parody song make several references to the transforming power of art and the great potential for democratization of this art (access/production/dissemination) that only the internet is capable of providing. Thus, in Caetano's own words (my emphasis): “*while men (Anjos tronchos) exercise their rotten powers*” , many things happen in the world that can dominate and destroy us, but “ *only/ Easter hermeticisms / And the tones, the thousand tones/ Their sounds and their genius gifts (art)/ They save us, they will save us/ From this darkness and nothing else...*” (CAETANO, *Podres Poderes* , 1984).

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